

Ion-Exchange Study of Manganese(III) Pyrophosphate

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Manuscript received 14 January 1977 ; accepted 18 March 1977

Manganese(III) pyrophosphate can be isolated from manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and selenium(IV) by passing through an anion exchanger De Acidite FF at $pH \approx 2.5$ and eluting it out by 1M tetra potassium pyrophosphate at $pH \approx 6$. The distribution coefficient has been determined. The effect of pH and concentration of tetrapotassium pyrophosphate on the elution of manganese(III) pyrophosphate has also been studied.

MANGANESE(III) compounds are strong oxidants and their stability depends upon the presence of complexing agents e. g. sulphate, fluoride or pyrophosphate¹. Manganese(III) pyrophosphate^{2,3,4} is stable over long periods and has been used as oxidant in visual, potentiometric and spectrophotometric titrations. Recently Bogdanovich⁵ et al have made a detailed study of the composition and stability of manganese(III) pyrophosphate. The present study describes an investigation of the ion exchange behaviour of manganese(III) pyrophosphate and its separation from manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and selenium(IV).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of E. Merck's guaranteed reagent grade. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiments. The anion exchange resin used was of Permutit's De Acidite FF in sulphate form (20-50 mesh). Manganese(III) pyrophosphate was prepared following Belcher and West² method and standardised spectrophotometrically with standard arsenic(III) solution. pH values were adjusted by means of dil. KOH/dil. H_2SO_4 .

The ion exchange column used was made of a glass tube of 10 mm diameter with a tap funnel at the top and glass wool at the bottom to support the resin bed. The bottom of the column was drawn to a narrow diameter and bent in double U shape so that the outlet was slightly higher than the top of the resin bed. The column was filled with 1.5g of air dried resin. Unicam SP 700A Spectrophotometer and Bausch & Lomb's Spectronic 20 were used for the absorbance measurements. Elico pH meter (Model LI-10) was used for pH measurements.

Determination of q and K_d

1g samples of the air dried resin were equilibrated for an hour with 20 ml solution of manganese(III) pyrophosphate at various pH values. The fraction of manganese(III) remained in the solution after equilibrium was determined spectrophotometrically⁶. Knowing the initial and the equilibrium concentrations of the manganese(III) in the external solution, the

amount, q , sorbed per 1g of the exchange material was calculated. K_d , the distribution coefficient values were calculated by the relation⁷

$$K_d = \frac{\text{Amount of Mn(III) in the resin}}{\text{Amount of Mn(III) in solution}} \times \frac{\text{ml, solution}}{\text{g, dry resin}}$$

The results are given in Table 1 and 2.

Elution Curves of Manganese(III) Pyrophosphate: 10 ml of $7.3 \times 10^{-8} M$ manganese(III) pyrophosphate solution at pH 2.5 was added to the column. The adsorbed species was then eluted with tetra potassium pyrophosphate of known concentration and pH value. The effluent was collected in fractions of 5 ml and each was analysed for the manganese(III). The concentration of manganese(III) was then plotted against the volume of effluent collected (Fig. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. Effect of pH of tetra potassium pyrophosphate on the elution of manganese(III) pyrophosphate.

Fig. 2. Effect of concentration of tetra potassium pyrophosphate on elution of manganese (III) pyrophosphate.

Separation of Manganese(III) Pyrophosphate

The column was thoroughly washed with 1% H_2SO_4 . Manganese(III) pyrophosphate solutions containing one of the foreign ions like manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and selenium(IV) were passed through the column at pH 2.5 with a flow rate of 0.25 ml per minute. Manganese(III) was fixed on the resin as $[Mn(H_2P_2O_7)_3]^{-3}$ leaving other ions in the effluent. The effluents were analysed by standard methods. Manganese(III) pyrophosphate was eluted with 50 ml of 1M tetrapotassium pyrophosphate at pH 6 with a flow rate of 0.75 - 1.50 ml per minute.

Results and Discussion

The dependence of q and K_d values on pH has been shown in Table 1. The K_d value increases as the pH changes from 1.0 to 2.5 and then becomes almost

constant upto pH 6. This is in consistent with the dissociation constant values of pyrophosphoric acid⁸ ($pK_1=0.85$, $pK_2=1.96$, $pK_3=6.54$ and $pK_4=8.44$). However, the slight decrease of K_d when pH is increased to 6 is possibly because of the preferential sorption of the free pyrophosphate on the resin.

Table 2 shows the effect of manganese(III) pyrophosphate concentration on q and K_d values. The decrease in K_d values at higher concentrations of manganese(III) pyrophosphate is due to the over loading on the resin. The constancy of K_d at different ratios of volume of solution to mass of resin is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF q & K_d VALUES OF MANGANESE(III) PYROPHOSPHATE ON THE CONCENTRATION OF MANGANESE (III).

Amount of the exchanger = 1g pH = 2.5		Total volume = 20 ml Temp = 26°C	
Amount of manganese (III), mg Before equilibrium	After equilibrium	q /1g m-equiv	K_d
11.77	4.69	0.39	30.19
12.95	4.96	0.44	32.22
14.95	5.89	0.49	30.76
17.66	8.01	0.53	24.09
21.00	11.50	0.52	16.52
24.00	14.28	0.53	13.61

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF q AND K_d VALUES ON MASS OF THE RESIN AND VOLUME OF THE SOLUTION.

pH = 2.5		Temp = 26°C			
Amount of the resin, g	Amount of manganese(III), mg Before equilibrium	After equilibrium	Total Vol. ml	q /1g m-equiv.	K_d
0.50	12.00	8.00	30	0.44	30.00
0.75	14.95	7.75	25	0.52	30.97
1.00	14.95	5.89	20	0.49	30.76
1.50	24.00	9.50	30	0.53	30.53
2.00	26.00	6.60	20	0.53	29.40

TABLE 4—SEPARATION OF MANGANESE(III) PYROPHOSPHATE FROM ADDED FOREIGN IONS.

Amount of the exchanger = 1.5 g		pH = 2.5		
Foreign ion	Foreign ion mg added,	Manganese(III) present, mg	Foreign ion recovered, mg	Manganese(III) recovered, mg
Mn(II)	27.69	1.16	27.67	1.16
	5.54	0.29	5.54	0.29
Co(II)	10.03	1.16	10.02	1.16
	2.01	5.44	2.00	5.43
Ni(II)	23.60	4.36	23.58	4.36
	5.60	2.18	5.59	2.17
Cu(II)	32.09	7.97	32.06	7.95
	12.84	3.22	12.82	3.21
Se(IV)	12.58	7.97	12.57	7.97
	2.29	3.99	2.28	3.98

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF q AND K_d VALUES OF MANGANESE(III) PYROPHOSPHATE ON pH.

Amount of the exchanger = 1g		Total volume = 20 ml Temp = 26°C		
pH	Amount of manganese (III) mg. Before equilibrium	After equilibrium	q /1g m-equiv.	K_d
1.0	12.09	6.32	0.32	18.26
1.5	12.09	5.57	0.35	23.41
2.0	12.09	4.91	0.39	29.25
2.5	12.95	4.96	0.44	32.22
3.0	12.09	4.69	0.40	31.55
4.0	12.09	4.69	0.40	31.55
5.0	12.10	4.90	0.39	29.39
6.0	12.10	5.10	0.38	27.45

The effects of pH and concentration of tetrapotassium pyrophosphate on the elution of manganese(III) pyrophosphate are shown in Fig. 1 and 2. The elution is fast, with sharper resolved peak with $1M$ tetrapotassium pyrophosphate at pH 6. The elution curve is nearly symmetrical and requires only 50 ml of eluent.

The results of separation of manganese(III) from manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and selenium(IV) are given in Table 4. Iron(III) forms anionic complex which is taken up by the resin and tellurium(IV) gives a precipitate with pyrophosphate and thus both cannot be separated from manganese(III) by this method.

This ion exchange method can successfully be adopted for the purification of manganese(III) pyrophosphate which can be used as an amperometric titrant for the determination of organic and inorganic complex materials.

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